

Original Article

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE OF ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE PACKAGES BY BUSINESS EDUCATION GRADUATE STUDENTS IN RIVERS STATE UNIVERSITIES AND THEIR EMPLOYABILITY REQUIREMENTS

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Phone Number: 08063908394

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17453893>

Abstract

The aim of the study was to determine the relationship between knowledge of accounting software packages and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State universities. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised 15 accounting education lecturers and 180 Business Education graduate students. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was not too large. Two sets of self-constructed questionnaire titled “Knowledge of accounting software packages (KASP)” and “Business Education graduate students’ employability requirements (BEGSER)” were used in collecting data for this study. The research instruments were validated by three experts; two Business Educators and one Measurement and Evaluation. Reliability level for the instruments was established using a test-re-test method. Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyse the two sets of data and the reliability coefficient values of 0.76 for two questionnaires. Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for answering the research questions while Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Method and t-transformation were used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed a positive relationship between Spreadsheet, Peachtree and Wave accounting software packages and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers Universities. The study shows a significant relationship between knowledge of spreadsheet, peachtree, and Wave Accounting.

Keywords: Accounting software packages, employability requirements, business education graduate students, spreadsheet and Peachtree.

Introduction

Accounting is a skill-based academic programme that enables an individual to know about the various economic events of their country through identifying, classifying, measuring and communicating the various activities to users of financial information for proper and accurate decision-making. William and Okoli, (2011) described Accounting as the language of business that can tell, to a reasonable accuracy, the degree of success an organization has achieved in its financial goals of profit and solvency. Accounting involves identifying, measuring, recording and

communicating financial information about our economic activities of an organization for management decision making (Ohaka&Agwor, 2017). Accounting is also defined as a process of identifying, recording of transactions, classifying, measuring of transactions, summarizing what has been recorded, interpreting and communicating economic events of an organization or an individual to interested users of the information (Kiabel, 2017). According to Stephenson (2017), the accounting process facilitates the analysis and interpretation of the financial transactions in a manner that makes them

comprehensible for the users to make appropriate decisions. Knowledge and skills in the usage of accounting software are invaluable for present day employment as many organizations have moved from the traditional manual record keeping to the digital system. It was in this light that Umoru (2020) averred that present day employers of labour look out for graduates of Accountancy Education that have competency in accounting software packages such as Sage Business Cloud, QuickBooks, Wave and Spread Sheet packages. Achieving effective Accountancy Education curriculum implementation should not be viewed as an event that should happen once but as a continuous cycle that requires relevant curriculum mapping, interpretation, implementation and review. A curriculum that recommends the use of emerging technologies such as accounting software packages prepares students of Accounting Education for employability because of the increasing attention to emerging technologies currently by employers of labour. Accounting Education involves the combination of different courses selected from business, economics, management, finance, marketing, administration, technology with foundational educational courses. International Finance Corporation (2019) rightly advised universities on the need to urgently make digital education curriculum shifts with an understanding that 50% of subject knowledge acquired during first year of a four-year technical degree will be out-dated by the time the students graduate. Consequently, Shaffer, Gaumer and Bradley (2020) asserted that there is a need for students to learn how to use specialized accounting software and gain a broad understanding on international financial accounting and commercial segment contexts. The authors posited that professional accountants also require adequate practical experiences on the use of generalized accounting software such as Tally, Peachtree and QuickBooks. Peachtree is an accounting software developed by Sage Software for small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs). Peachtree enables controllers and managers to automate and manage numerous accounting tasks like reconciling accounts payable and receivable, creating financial statements, checking invoices, tracking banking transfers and payroll, importing and manipulating spreadsheets, integrating scanned documents such as checks, receipts and invoices by eliminating paper from the accounting process. Peachtree accounting software comes in five different versions, namely: Pro, Complete, Premium, Quantum, and Accountant version. Peachtree Pro is

the base version that has basic functionality and is the cheapest. Peachtree Premium adds additional functionality with advanced budgeting functionality and a few other tools. Peachtree Quantum is what is used at the manufacturing company to take care of our corporate books while Quantum adds more functionality geared more towards accountants and larger businesses. One of the great advantages of using Peachtree is that users can be up and run under a half-hour. Users do not have to know much or anything about accounting to set it up. Follow the onscreen guide and it will take users step-by-step through the setup process that includes setting up all of the company information, customers, vendors, inventory or service items, employees, chart of general ledger accounts, and security. For the general ledger accounts, Peachtree offers the ability to choose from preloaded accounts or can be setup” (Eric, 2020). Peachtree is a fully functional accounting system that allows you to issue invoices to your customers, receives payments, enters payables to your vendors, print checks, pays your employees, tracks expenses, enters journal entries, and much more. It is packed with all kinds of different preloaded reports. Peachtree also will perform an internal accounting review that will identify common transaction mistakes” (Eric, 2020). Another great benefit of using Peachtree is that you do not need an accounting degree to use it. It is as simple as finding the button on the screen and clicking on it which will bring up the appropriate window where you can enter all of the information that you need to. In Peachtree changes can be made depending on security clearance however, any change in a prior period, will change your financial results in that period. Another advantage of using Peachtree is that it is a cost-effective solution. It depends on the version that is been purchase according to their website and make purchase from local office supply store. Peachtree comes loaded with a large number of reports that are all customizable in some way.

Statement of the Problem

Accounting Education graduates who are not adequately equipped with accounting software competencies required for gainful employment will keep roaming the streets in search of white collar jobs (Oguejiofor, 2020). Robert and Precious (2017) observed that most industries, government and private organizations lament over the inability of Accountancy Education graduates to perform efficiently in employment especially in the use of accounting software. These challenges have made organizations to engage the services of consultants to

train their accounting graduate employees on the practical application of modern accounting software packages for a period of time after which only few will be retained out of many as a result of not meeting up with company's requirements for employment after the training. In view of the cost and time spent in retraining these graduates on the use of different accounting software packages, many researchers and stakeholders have attributed the problems to the inability of higher institutions that are saddled with this responsibility to adequately expose Accounting Education graduates on the practical application of modern accounting software packages during the course of their training. The problem of this study is that the inability of universities and other higher educational institutions to adequately equip Accounting Education graduates with accounting software packages could be because they are not sufficiently emphasized in the curriculum. Lack of competency in the use of accounting software packages could be a contributory factor to the high unemployment rate of Accounting Education graduates from universities in Rivers State. The problem could also be as a result of the curriculum designers and lecturers not being aware of the relationship between accounting education students' proficiency in accounting software packages and their employability requirements in the digital business and office environments. This makes the study imperative as it will provide empirical data to facilitate objective remedial actions by the relevant stakeholders to ensure that Accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State are adequately equipped for gainful employment and efficient duty performance.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between knowledge of accounting software packages and employability requirements skills of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between knowledge of spreadsheet accounting software package and employability requirements of business education graduate students in rivers state universities.
2. Determine the relationship between knowledge of peachtree accounting software package and employability requirements of business education graduate students in rivers state universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between knowledge of Spread sheet accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?
2. What is the relationship between knowledge of Peachtree accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between knowledge in Spread sheet accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduates in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significant relationship between knowledge in Peachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduates in Rivers State Universities.

Method

The research design adopted for this study was correlational survey research design meant to determine the relationship between Accounting Software Packages and Employability Requirements of Business Education graduates in Rivers State Universities. Correlational survey design basically involves the extraction of information from respondents through the distribution of questionnaire and/or interview to check the authenticity of the relationship between any two variables. The population of this study consisted of 220 (15 lecturers and 180 graduate students) of Business Education (Accounting Education option) of 2023/2024 Academic year in RSU and IAUE. The entire population was studied without sampling as the size was not too large instruments for data collection were researchers'-developed questionnaires titled "Knowledge of accounting software packages (KASP)" and "Business Education graduate students' employability requirements (BEGSER)". The instruments were on a 4-point rating scale with strongly agree (SA), agree (A) disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). Data collected were analysed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) to answer the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. T-transformation was used to test for the strength of the hypotheses. The decision rule was that the null hypotheses were retained when the critical r value was greater than the calculated r value; otherwise, they were settled for the alternate.

Table 1: Analysis of Relationship between knowledge of Spreadsheet accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

(N= 195)

S/No	Variables	Responses	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-crit	Dec.
1	Spread sheet accounting software package (X)	3,633				Positive Relationship
			57,098	0.98	± 0.1476	Exist
2	employability requirements of Business Education graduate students (Y)	2,813				

Researcher’s Field Survey (2024)

The table shows that the calculated r was 0.98 which is higher than the table value of ± 0.1476 . This means that a positive relationship exists between knowledge of Spreadsheet accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State universities.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between knowledge of Peachtree accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Analysis of relationship between knowledge of Peachtree accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

(N= 195)

S/No	Variables	Responses	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-crit	Dec.
1	Peachtree accounting software package (X)	3,635				Positive Relationship
			53,126	0.70	± 0.1476	Exist
2	employability requirements of Business Education graduate students (Y)	2,813				

The table shows that the calculated r was 0.70 with the table value of 0.1476. This means that since the calculated r is higher than the table value, a positive relationship exist between knowledge of Peachtree

accounting software package and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students.

Table 3: Summary of calculated r of Significant Relationship between the knowledge in Spread sheet accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

S/No	Variables	$\sum XY$	r-cal	t-trans	t-crit	Decision
1	Spread sheet accounting software package					Positive Relationship
		57,098	0.98	2.40	± 1.645	Exist
2	employability requirements of Business Education graduate students					

N= 195 Df= 193 P>0.05 * = Significant

Table 3 shows the calculated coefficient (r) value of 0.98 with N = 195 at 193 degrees of freedom and alpha level of 0.05. Since the r value is greater than the alpha level (P>0.05), it shows that a significant positive relationship exists between the knowledge in Spread sheet accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities. The null

hypothesis was, therefore, rejected. Table 3 further shows a t-transformation value of 2.40 which is greater than the critical t value of ± 1.645 further indicating a strong relationship between Spread sheet accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4: Summary of calculated r of Significant Relationship between the knowledge in Peachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

S/No	Variables	$\sum XY$	r-cal	t-trans	t-crit	Decision
1	Peachtree accounting software package	53,126	0.70	3.76	±1.645	Positive Relationship
2	employability requirements of Business Education graduate students					Exist

N= 195 Df= 193 P>0.05 * = Significant
 Table 4, shows the calculated coefficient (r) value of significant relationship between the knowledge in Peachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities. With N= 195, Df= 193, P>0.05, the calculated r was 0.70 with critical t value of ±1.645 at P>0.05 level of significance and since the calculated r value was statistically greater than the table value, the null hypotheses therefore was rejected and the conclusion is that there is a relationship between Sage Business Cloud accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities. Further showed a t-transformation value of 3.76 with a t-critical value of ±1.645. This means that since the t-transformation value is statistically greater than the t-critical table value, there is a strong relationship between Peachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities. The value of r was therefore accepted, which indicated that there is significant relationship between knowledge of Peachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion

Findings of the study on the relationship between knowledge of Spreadsheet accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State universities revealed a significant positive relationship between the variables. This is because Spread sheet accounting software package prepares graduates with computing data accuracy, creation of standard budget, graphs and charts representation of financial information, data retrieval after being saved for a long time and enhances the use mathematical formulas. This finding agrees with of Claudio (2016) that what makes a spread sheet software program unique is its ability to calculate values using mathematical formulas and the data in cells. The findings further indicated that

statistically significant relationship exist between knowledge of Spreadsheet accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduates in Rivers State Universities. The first findings revealed that Peachtree accounting software package prepares graduates for bank reconciliation, creating financial statements, tracking banking transfers and payroll, reporting of financial information, importing and manipulating of spread sheet and integrating of scanned documents like receipts and invoices. The findings is in line with the work Eric (2020), Peachtree is a fully functional accounting system that allows you to issue invoices to your customers, receives payments, enters payables to your vendors, print checks, pays your employees, tracks expenses, enters journal entries, and much more. It is packed with all kinds of different preloaded reports. Peachtree also will perform an internal accounting review that will identify common transaction mistakes. The conclusion was that there was positive relationship knowledge ofPeachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students. Based on the first findings, “a hypothetical test was conducted which also indicated that statistically significant exist between knowledge ofPeachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduates in Rivers State Universities. The test further revealed that in line with the work of Eric (2020) Peachtree enables controllers and managers to automate and manage numerous accounting tasks like reconciling accounts payable and receivable, creating financial statements, check invoices, tracking banking transfers and payroll, importing and manipulating spread sheets, integrating scanned documents such as checks, receipts and invoices, eliminating paper from the accounting process. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship statistically exist between knowledge ofPeachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduates since the calculated of the correlation coefficient (r) value was statistically greater than the

table value $P > 0.05$ level of significance, the null hypotheses therefore, was rejected at $P > 0.05$ of significance. The strength of the relationship was determined with a t-transformation test which was concluded on the calculated correlation coefficient value (r), which indicated that a statistically significant relationship exist between knowledge of Peachtree accounting software package and employability of Business Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.”

Conclusion

Findings of this study revealed that a significant positive relationship exists between knowledge of Spreadsheet and Peachtree accounting software packages and employability requirements of Business Education graduate students of Rivers State universities. Based on these findings, the researcher concluded that knowledge of accounting software packages is very important for Business Education graduates to meet employability requirements in the current digital office and business environments. Competencies in the usage of accounting software packages will help the graduates to become more relevant in the labour market by securing and progressing in employment to reduce the level of unemployment and poverty in the society.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations:

1. Business Education curriculum developers should emphasize knowledge and skills in utilization of accounting software packages in order to equip graduates to secure and progress in employment in the digital era. Accounting software packages inclusion of the software packages into the curriculum should be encourage by planners for sustainable graduates' marketability.
2. Business education lecturers should ensure that Spreadsheet software packages are regularly used by Business Education graduate students.
3. Lecturers should encourage Business Education graduate students to undergo training on the current accounting software packages programmes.

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